

CASTANIBUS

Introduction

CASTANIBUS unites the BIODIVERSAMENTE CASTAGNO and CASTANI-CO OGs, whose primary objectives are to identify and share "guidelines for the study, preservation and valorisation of the chestnut tree and the best management of chestnut groves to obtain a quality product", to revalorise the "culture of chestnut cultivation" and the role of the chestnut grower as a quality producer and guardian of the mountain territory.

CASTANIBUS was a two-day journey that networked all the realities that revolve around the chestnut tree and the need for protection and development in the Apennines, from carbon sequestration to the protection of biodiversity, fostering a proactive and constructive exchange between researchers, GO partner farmers and regional officials, with the main players involved in chestnut cultivation in Emilia Romagna.

Concentrating the participants on the coach made it possible to favour an exchange of experiences and opinions on the reality of chestnut cultivation, but above all to bring the comparison to the field by visiting chestnut groves and Metati.

The bus tour made it possible to make the best possible use of the travelling time from Bologna, the place of departure, to Marola, facilitating an exchange of experiences and opinions on the reality of chestnut cultivation, but above all to take the comparison to the field by visiting chestnut groves and Metati.

The trip was full of speeches and moments of discussion concerning the current situation and future prospects of regional chestnut cultivation after extremely difficult years for producers due to the Chinese wasp, which has now been eradicated thanks to the interventions of the Regional Phytosanitary Service.

Lessons learned

The partnership between the actors of the OGs demonstrated the effectiveness of 'networking', a fundamental condition for sharing and integrating in practice market requirements with environmental and scientific innovation, and human, historical, cultural and landscape heritage.

The bus tour with the various territorial actors active in the chestnut sector was a good way to stimulate and bring them into the field. One of the most important result was the desire and the concrete possibility of activating a Regional Plan for Chestnut Growing as a result of the cooperation between the Emilia-Romagna Region and the Consortia of Chestnut Growers, some of which were united in a coordination, and other public and private stakeholders.

For further information contact

Carla Paola Scotti, Project Coordinator, Italy, email: scotti@pedologia.net

Livia Antisari, Professor, University of Bologna, Italy, email: livia.vittori@unibo.it

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.pedologia.net/it/BIODIVERSAMENTE->

[CASTAGNO/cms/Pagina.action?pageAction=&page=InfoSuolo.47&localeSite=it](https://www.pedologia.net/it/BIODIVERSAMENTE-CASTAGNO/cms/Pagina.action?pageAction=&page=InfoSuolo.47&localeSite=it)

<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/castani-co-%E2%80%99Cil-sequestro-di-carbonio-nel-sistema.html>

--	--	---	---